

Banner Programs: A Triangulation Assessment by the Selected Teachers and School Heads on Its Implementation in the Division of Cavite

Ma. Theresa E. Obrero ■ Basilisa R. Digma ■ Elpidia B. Bergado

Abstract

The study focused on the deliberate assessment of the Banner Programs of the division aligned to the core thrusts of DepEd classified as Access, Quality, and Governance. This research utilized the descriptive-comparative-quantitative research design. A selected 150 elementary teachers and 35 secondary teachers together with the 37 school heads were identified as participants of the study through random sampling technique. Frequency and Mean Percentage score were used to determine the level of implementation of the Banner Programs while ANOVA was used to determine whether there are any statistically significant difference between the assessment of the public school principals, public elementary and secondary teachers, and the division-based personnel reports. Access and Quality Banner Programs were assessed with P-value of 0.0095 and 0.0015 respectively, there is a significant difference on the triangulation assessment of the teachers, school principals and the gathered data on the implementation of the programs. The null hypotheses were rejected. The study is limited to the 10 Banner Programs of the division with direct influenced to the learners and the teachers. This is contributory to continuous improvement and sustainability of the implementation of the Quality Management Improvement of the division.

Keywords: Assessment. Banner programs. Access. Quality. Governance.

Ma. Theresa E. Obrero*

*DepEd - Bagong Pook Elementary School, Trece Martires, Cavite
matheresa.obrero@deped.gov.ph*

Basilisa R. Digma

*DepEd - Hugo Perez Elementary School, Trece Martires, Cavite
basilisa.digma@deped.gov.ph*

Elpidia B. Bergado

*DepEd - Division of Cavite, Philippines
elpidia.bergado@deped.gov.ph*

*Corresponding author

Introduction

In accordance to the Republic Act No. 9155 (RA 9155) or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, the mandate and vision, mission, and core values (VMCV) of the institution were pronounced wherein the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) together with the Assistant Schools Division Superintendents (ASDS), as its senior leaders, lead the Schools Division Office of Cavite Province. They set the direction of the division through its strategic Division Education Development Plan (DEDP).

The division mantra #ParaSaBatangKabitenyo is a clear overarching advocacy and commitment for relevant, accessible, inclusive, and quality basic education of Cavite learners through its exemplar curriculum implementation and school governance and operations recognized in the entire. In order to sustain the commitment to excellence and continuous improvement, the SDS launches an annual tagline wherein the tagline for 2019, "Gamechanger: Raising the Bar, Reinventing the Norm", which strengthens the division as an industry lead in giving the direction of other divisions in observance of the Transparent, Ethical, and Accountable (TEA) Governance to foster legal and ethical behavior in all interactions.

Through this mantra, the division of Cavite formulated and implemented the Division Banner Programs as the Division Key Performance Indicators classified into three goals such as: Access, Quality, and Governance. The programs/projects under the goal to improve access through universal participation are: Project KALINGA (*Kapwa Ko, Alay Lingkod*), Project OK (*Oplan Kalusugan*) sa DepEd, and Project SHED (Students' Home for Education and Development); in goal to improve the learning outcomes under the Quality are: Project AGAP (Advancing Global Awareness Possibilities), Project Power It Up, Project SPARK (Sustainable Practical Approach to Reading for Kids), Project I-Likha (*Integrasyon ng Lokalidad, Iugnay sa Karunungan at Hubog na Aralin*), Project SALIKSURI, and Project HI-TEACH (Highly Integral Teachers' Empowerment Amplified with Collaboration and Hard work); and under Governance, the goal to improve the efficiency and governance of the division is the Project PRO LEAD (Lead, Empower and Achieve through Data-Driven Decisions).

Along with this context, the aforesaid banner programs of Cavite encompasses to the purpose of delivering quality education and systematic flow of the organization. **Project KALINGA** focused on the proactive, preventive, inclusive and formative learners interventions aims to achieve zero out-of-school children and youth in all barangays in the Province of Cavite and address school leavers and out-of-school youth problem in the division, particularly on the secondary level. In **Project OK sa DEPED** anchored to the different Projects such as Wash in School (WINS), School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP), Medical and Nursing, Dental Services, Adolescence Health Reproduction Program, Mental Health Education Program, and National Drug Education Program (NDEP). To strengthen the student's organization in school such

as Supreme Pupil Government (SPG), Supreme Student Government (SSG), Youth for Environment in Schools Organization (Yes-O), Boy Scouts of the Philippines (BSP), and Girl Scouts of the Philippines (GSP), the guidance services offered by the school encompass the **Project SHED**.

In **Project AGAP**, this includes preparation and evaluation of assessment tools, analysis of assessment results which serve as data for Instructional Supervision, monitoring and evaluations and crafting of intervention plans to address learning gaps, adjust instruction, and track students' progress based on learning standards. **Project Power It Up** is designed to meet the needs of all types of learners by addressing learning gaps, achieving required skills, and unleashing students' full potential both within and outside the classroom. **Project Spark** along with the Program Power It Up focused on the reading activities of the school which aims to empower learners that reading is fun and easy leading to the regression of the non-readers in school. **Project I-Likha** focused on contextualizing instructional materials of different kinds addressing the needs of our 21st learners and serves as support teaching aids to the teachers. **Project Salik-Suri** aims to develop research studies relative to curriculum implementation, utilization of findings and policy formulations based on researches. **Project HI-TEACH** is created to conduct Team Based Instructional Supervision as the foundation for providing Technical Assistance in terms of content and pedagogy, to capacitate school heads in the exercise of Instructional Leadership through process observation, coaching and mentoring schemes, and to build capability for all instructional leaders in all learning areas throughout the division, while the **Project PROLEAD** includes the teaching and learning capacity building, as well as the human resource development.

Out of this concept, Irvine and Crowley (2013), states that Educational assessment, according to the British Columbia Ministry of Education, is the "process of gathering evidence of what a student knows, understands, is able to do and is working towards." He added that, according to the Curriculum and Assessment Framework Advisory Group of British Columbia which formed in November 2011, all assessment activities should focus on five cross-curricular learning abilities (communication, critical thinking, creative thinking and innovation, personal responsibility and well-being, and social responsibility), as well as learning standards for the age and subject (under development). Thus, according to the Standards for Registered Training Organisations 2015, an assessment system is a coordinated collection of established rules and procedures (including assessment materials and tools) that guarantee assessments are consistent and based on the Principles of Assessment and the Rules of Evidence.

The Department of Education (DepEd) - Cavite determines its key service and work process requirements by remaining committed to its mandate. Periodic program reporting and performance review were observed in order to monitor the progress on teacher and student performances. In this concept, the triangulation assessment of the teachers, school heads and the division-based personnel reports regarding on the Banner Programs Implementation came its inception to further validate the status and direct impact of the implementation of the programs up to the school level in both elementary and secondary schools in the Division of Cavite for the benefit of the Batang Caviteño.

Research Questions

The main purpose of the study is to monitor and assess the banner programs implemented in the division as it was assessed by the teachers, school heads, and the division-based personnel reports. The tool was validated by the curriculum experts and planners as well. The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of implementation of the banner programs under **Access** (Project Kalinga, Project OK sa DepEd, Project SHED) in the division of Cavite as assessed by the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports?
2. Along with the **Quality** (Projects AGAP, I-Likha, Power It Up, SPARK, SALIKSURI, and HI-TEACH) based on the assessment of the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports, what is the level of implementation of the banner programs in the division of Cavite?
3. According to the assessment of the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports, what is the level of implementation of the projects, programs, and activities (PPAs) in the division of Cavite on the Governance aspect in Project PROLEAD?
4. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports on the level of implementation of the banner programs in the division of Cavite under **Access** (Projects Kalinga, Ok sa DepEd, and SHED)?
5. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports on the level of implementation of the banner programs in the division of Cavite in **Quality** (Projects AGAP, I-Likha, Power It Up, SPARK, and SALIKSURI)?
6. Based from the results, what is the future direction of the study?

Research Hypotheses

The null hypotheses were tested in this study using the 0.05 level of significance.

Ho: There are no significant differences between the assessment of the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports on the level of implementation of the Banner Programs in the division of Cavite under **Access** (Projects Kalinga, Ok sa DepEd, and SHED).

Ho: There are no significant differences between the assessment of the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports on the level of implementation of the Banner Programs in the division of Cavite in **Quality** (Projects AGAP, I-Likha, Power It Up, SPARK, SALIKSURI, and HI-TEACH).

Scope and Limitation

The study focused on the assessment of the 37 public school principals, 185 public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports on the level of implementation of the banner programs in the division of Cavite. Hence, the division has 12 banner programs and projects implemented; the researchers tend to limit the aforesaid 10 banner programs classified into three goals such as: **Access**, **Quality**, and **Governance**.

The monitoring and assessment tool utilized in the study undergoes to the validation process of the curriculum planners and experts before it was used in the study.

Methodology

This research utilized the quantitative type of research. Specifically, it involves a descriptive-comparative-quantitative research design. According to Balnaves and Caputi (2001), quantitative research is the systematic study of phenomena via the collection of measurable data and the use of statistical, mathematical, or computational methodologies. It collects data from current and potential participants using sampling methods, the results of which may be represented numerically. This research design is suitable for obtaining the study's most important findings.

Sampling

In this study, the researchers used the simple random sampling in selecting the participants of the study. Out of 333 elementary schools and 72 secondary schools, 30 elementary schools (150 teachers) and seven secondary schools (35 teachers) together with the 37 school heads were the participants of the study.

In simple random sampling, every member of the population has an equal chance of being chosen for the sample. This sampling methodology is appropriate for the objectives of the study, which includes removing bias from the selection process and producing representative samples.

Data Collection

In this study, the researchers sought to gather data on the implementation of the banner programs through the researcher made questionnaire from the 185 teacher-participants and 37 school heads. The researchers furnish permission and proper correspondence to the district supervisors, the school administrators, and the teacher-participants to gather reliable data and to assure that the data gathering procedure adheres to protocols and scholarly methods.

Distributions of questionnaires were done through the help of the district office wherein the school is located as well as the retrieval of the responses of the participants. The researchers ensure that highest ethical protocols will be observed and adhered to maintain the scholarly conduct and integrity of research due to the fact that the participants of the study are human participants. The researchers assure and maintain the confidentiality of the information and anonymity of the teacher-participants.

Ethical Issues

The researchers ensured that highest ethical protocols were observed and adhered to maintain the scholarly conduct and integrity of research. The researchers assured and maintained the confidentiality of the information and anonymity of the respondents. The records of the findings are well kept and secured by the researchers.

Data Analysis

In response to the study's statement of the problem, quantitative and descriptive statistical analysis was used to treat the data gathered. The following statistical tools used to analyze and interpret the data:

1. Frequency and Mean were used to determine the level of implementation of the banner programs in the division of Cavite as assessed by the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports on the level of implementation of the banner programs in the division of Cavite under **Access** (Project Kalinga, OK sa DepEd, SHED), **Quality** (Projects AGAP, I-Likha, Power It Up, SPARK, SALIKSURI, and HI-TEACH), and **Governance** with Project LEAD.
2. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine whether there are any statistically significant difference between the assessment of the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports on the level of implementation of the banner programs in the division of Cavite in terms of **Access** (Projects Kalinga, OK sa DepEd, and SHED), **Quality** (Projects AGAP, I-Likha, Power It Up, SPARK, SALIKSURI, and HI-TEACH), and **Governance** in Project PROLEAD.

Results and Discussion

In this study, the researchers used the simple random sampling in selecting the participants of the study. Out of 333 elementary schools and 72 secondary schools, 30 elementary schools (150 teachers) and seven secondary schools (35 teachers) together with the 37 school heads were the participants of the study.

In simple random sampling, every member of the population has an equal chance of being chosen for the sample. This sampling methodology is appropriate for the objectives of the study, which includes removing bias from the selection process and producing representative samples.

Statistical Treatment

The findings of the study were systematically presented, analyzed, and interpreted following the sequence of the research questions as enumerated previously. The legend used in the assessment and interpretation in objectives 1 to 3 is as follows:

Table 1 Students' concerns on the OBE implementation

Likert Scale	Mean Interval Scoring	Interpretation
4	3.26-4.00	Exemplary
3	2.51-3.25	Proficient
2	1.76-2.50	Developing
1	1.00-1.75	Emerging

Objective #1. The level of implementation of the banner programs under Access (Project Kalinga, Project OK sa DepEd, Project SHED) in the division of Cavite as assessed by the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports.

Table 2 Level of implementation of the banner programs under ACCESS

	Banner Programs					
	Kalinga		OK sa DepEd		SHED	
	Ave. Mean	Indicator	Ave. Mean	Indicator	Ave. Mean	Indicator
Participants						
Teachers	2.99	Proficient	2.81	Proficient	2.56	Proficient
School heads	3.42	Exemplary	3.47	Exemplary	3.50	Exemplary
Division-based reports	2.80	Proficient	1.81	Developing	1.50	Developing
TOTAL	3.07	Proficient	2.70	Proficient	2.85	Developing
ACCESS Ave. Mean	2.87		Proficient			

The triangulation assessment of the participants namely: teachers, school heads, and the division-based personnel reports showed that program and projects implemented by the division of Cavite under the Key Performing Areas: Access has a general average mean score of 2.87 which indicates that the level of implementation is Proficient. Hence, the school heads rated the program and project 3.42, 3.47, and 3.50 respectively with exemplary status of implementation while the teachers and the division-based personnel reports assessment indicated the Proficient and Developing level of implementation. These results implied that there is an inconsistency of assessment in the three different angle/level of the programs and projects implementation that the division senior leaders should take into consideration in making decisions.

Objective #2. The level of implementation of the banner programs under Quality (Project AGAP, Project Power It Up, Project SPARK, Project I-LIKHA, Project SALIKSURI, Project HI-TEACH) in the division of Cavite as assessed by the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports.

Table 3 Level of implementation of the banner programs under QUALITY (Projects AKAP, Power It Up, and SPARK)

	Banner Programs					
	AKAP		Power It Up		SPARK	
	Ave. Mean	Indicator	Ave. Mean	Indicator	Ave. Mean	Indicator
Participants						
Teachers	3.08	Proficient	2.98	Proficient	3.09	Proficient
School heads	3.58	Exemplary	3.57	Exemplary	3.55	Exemplary
Division-based reports	3.20	Proficient	3.20	Proficient	3.67	Exemplary
TOTAL	3.29	Exemplary	3.25	Proficient	3.44	Exemplary

Table 4 Level of implementation of the banner programs under QUALITY (Projects I-LIKHA, SALIKSURI, and HI-TEACH)

	Banner Programs					
	I-LIKHA		SALIKSURI		HI-TEACH	
	Ave. Mean	Indicator	Ave. Mean	Indicator	Ave. Mean	Indicator
Participants						
Teachers	2.58	Proficient	2.09	Developing	2.79	Proficient
School heads	3.42	Exemplary	2.63	Proficient	3.47	Proficient
Division-based reports	2.40	Developing	1.00	Emerging	2.89	Proficient
TOTAL	2.80	Proficient	1.91	Developing	3.05	Proficient
QUALITY Ave. Mean	2.96		Proficient			

The previous table revealed that out of six programs and projects under the Key Performance Indicators of the Division which is Quality, Project AGAP has a general mean score of 3.29 and viewed as with Exemplary implementation. However, in Project SALIKSURI, it has its Developing level of implementation with 1.91 average mean score assessed by the teachers, school heads, and the division-based personnel reports and the general average mean score of the programs and projects under the Quality Key Performance Indicators of the division of Cavite was 2.96 and it was implemented proficiently.

Objective #3. The level of implementation of the banner programs under Access (Project PROLEAD) in the division of Cavite as assessed by the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports.

Table 5 Level of implementation of the banner programs under GOVERNANCE (Project PROLEAD)

Participants	Ave. Mean	Indicator
Teachers	2.86	Proficient
School heads	3.45	Exemplary
Division-based reports	3.20	Proficient
TOTAL	3.17	Proficient

Based on the accumulated results of the triangulated assessment, the school heads assessed exemplary implementation of the Project PRO-LEAD with an average mean score of 3.45. Though, the teachers and the division-based personnel reports weighed up into proficient level of implementation with an average mean of 2.86 and 3.20, respectively. It implies that even the Banner Program Implementation has the same purpose or direction were set by the senior leaders in the division, the degree or level of implementation varies to the hierarchy of position in the educational curriculum structure.

Objective #4. The significant difference on the level of implementation of the banner programs under Access (Project Kalinga, Project OK sa DepEd, Project SHED) in the division of Cavite as assessed by the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports.

The succeeding table provides the significant difference of the triangulated assessment of the teachers, school heads, and the division-based personnel reports.

Table 6 Significant difference on the implementation of the banner programs under ACCESS

Profile	f-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Triangulated assessment	8.9562	.00158	Reject Ho	With Significant Difference

Based from the result of the inferential statistical analysis using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), the table revealed that the f-value was 8.9562 and the p-value was 0.0158 and significant at 0.05 level. This means that there exists a significant difference among the assessment of the teachers, school heads, and the division-based personnel reports when they assessed the Banner Program Implementation.

Therefore, the null hypothesis stated previously that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the implementation of the division banner programs when grouped according to the triangulated assessment of the teachers, school heads, and the division-based personnel reports should be rejected. Statistically, despite the apparent consistency in the participants' consensus and ratings, there is a significant difference in the evaluation they provided.

Objective #5. The significant difference on the implementation of the banner programs under Quality (Project AGAP, Project Power It Up, Project SPARK, Project I-LIKHA, Project SALIKSURI, Project HI-TEACH) in the division of Cavite as assessed by the public school principals, public elementary and high school teachers, and from the division-based personnel reports.

Table 7 Significant difference on the implementation of the banner programs under QUALITY

Profile	f-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Triangulated assessment	1.9868	0.1716	Accept Ho	Without Significant Difference

The findings of the study on the significant difference of the Key Performance Indicators in the division of Cavite under Quality, the following Banner Programs such as: Project AGAP, Project Power It Up, Project SPARK, Project I-LIKHA, Project SALIKSURI, Project HI-TEACH showed that there is no significant difference among the assessment of the teachers, school heads, and the division-based personnel reports with its f-value of 1.9868 and the p-value of 0.1716 and significant at 0.05 level. Regardless of the incongruence of the assessed data, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Objective #6. The future direction of the study.

Based on the findings of the study, it is evident that seven out of ten Banner Programs implemented rated as Proficient in its implementation, the two other programs were assessed exemplary level of implementation namely: Project AGAP and SPARK with an average mean of 3.29 and 3.44, respectively; however, Project SALIKSURI gained 1.91 average mean score which is in the Developing stage of implementation.

Ultimately the results of the study are sufficient evidence to confirm the impact of the banner programs which serves as the mirror-view of the outcome of the strategic plan formulated by the senior leaders in the division composed of the division planning team. Despite of the rigid implementation, the three-point level of assessment realizes the contributory and drawback factors of the program that need to be address appropriately. Further studies may focus on the added factors or on the regression analysis on the determination of these factors whether or not they serve as determinants of the improvement of the quality service of the educational personnel of the division of Cavite for the benefit of the learners.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The salient points of the study portray that the assessment of the participants as it was triangulated by the teachers, school heads, and the division-based personnel reports acknowledge the level of implementation of the division banner programs that would serve as the basis for the continuous development of the programs implemented by the division. The study also considerably showed the affirmative reception of the participants towards the implementation. Project OK sa Deped and Project SHED showed incongruency on the triangulated assessment under Access. Under the Quality Key Performance Indicators, Program implementation viewed indistinctively triangulated assessment results. Based on the findings of the study, it is evident that seven out of ten Banner Programs implemented rated as Proficient in its implementation, the two other programs were assessed exemplary level of implementation namely: Project AGAP and SPARK with an average mean of 3.29 and 3.44 respectively however, Project SALIKSURI gained 1.91 average mean score which is in the Developing stage of implementation.

Through this study, The Department of Education Division of Cavite may utilize the results as the basis for the continuous development of the programs implemented by the division. It is recommended to revisit the implementation plan to identify the gaps towards the implementation process, to review the matrix of the programs to have the synoptic assessment of the indicators in order to have a holistic approach, and to conduct another studies that may focus on the impact of the Banner programs.

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